

Modified e-slotted patch antenna for WLAN/Wi-Max satellite applications

Akanksha Gupta¹, D. K. Srivastava², J. P. Saini³

¹Institute of Engineering and Technology, Bundelkhand University, Jhansi, India

²Bundelkhand Institute of Engineering and Technology, Jhansi, India

³Netaji Subhash University of Technology, Delhi, India

Article Info

Article history:

Received Apr 18, 2019

Revised Jun 24, 2019

Accepted Jul 18, 2019

Keywords:

Microstrip antenna

Multiple applications

Wi-Max

Wireless local area network

ABSTRACT

A low profile modified e-slotted microstrip antenna is proposed for multiple wireless communication applications. The performance of antenna is measured in terms of return loss, current distribution. The effect of variation of height of substrate on antenna impedance bandwidth is also studied. The antenna with overall size $30 \times 50 \times 0.8 \text{ mm}^3$ resonates at eight frequencies which covers some important applications like GPS, wireless local area network (WLAN), worldwide interoperability for microwave access (WiMax), Satellite communication etc. The proposed antenna structure offers great advantages due to compact size, simple structure and multiple applications. The multi band antenna was designed and optimized using ansoft HFSS v13 simulator. The simulated result is good agreement with measured result.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Akanksha Gupta,

Institute of Engineering and Technology,

Bundelkhand University,

Jhansi, India.

Email: akku.gupta6@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid progression of wireless system accelerate interest in multiband, low cost, light weighted, compact patch antennas however the conventional microstrip antennas suffer with several limitations such as narrow bandwidth, low gain and low efficiency. To overcome these limitations many researchers worked on it since the 1980s [1-5], still the research is in process to design compact size, multiband and high gain patch antennas. Now a days it is desirable to design an antenna which integrate as many applications such as GPS, wireless area network (WLAN) Wi-Fi, Wi-Max, RFID, into a single device. For this reasons many designs like dual band F-shape printed monopole antenna [5], multi band slot antenna [6], defected ground (DGS) multi band patch antenna [7], triple band e-shape patch antenna [8], stub loaded multi band slotted antenna [9], tri-band microstrip antenna [10] and triple band fractal microstrip antenna [11] have been proposed. Compact multiband monopole [12] had small size of $30 \times 34 \times 0.8 \text{ mm}^3$ but the design is complex in structure and the maximum antenna gain is -1 dBi for 2 GHz, 1 dBi for 3.5 GHz, and 3.5 dBi for 5 GHz, e-slot antenna in [8] has maximum gain at two resonant frequencies is 1.5 dBi and total size of antenna is $80 \times 100 \times 1.6 \text{ mm}^3$, the dual band monopole antenna in [6] had size $35 \times 40 \times 1.6 \text{ mm}^3$ with gain 1.87 dBi at 2.45 GHz frequency and 2.88 dBi at 5.18 GHz. In regular microstrip antenna the dual, triple and multi band response are obtained with respect to fundamental and next higher order mode resonance frequency, but the radiation pattern characteristics not remains constant over two, three or multi frequencies [8].

2. METHODOLOGY

In this proposed work the multi band operation is obtained by slot cutting method, for the identical radiation pattern characteristic as we cut the slot on the patch the higher order modes is generated near to the fundamental mode which broaden the impedance bandwidth [9]. The location of the feed strip has a significant effect on impedance bandwidth and radiation characteristics. A single layer, compact multi band microstrip antenna is described. Parametric study of different parameters is also reported to obtain the best results. The proposed antenna is better than the work studied in literature which is shown with the help of Table 1.

Table1. Comparison with reference work

Ref. Ant.	No. of band	Antenna dimensions	Resonant frequency (GHz)	Total size
[6]	2	35×40×1.6	2.45, 5.18	2240m.m. ³
[8]	3	80 × 100 ×1.59	.738, .922, .970	12720m.m. ³
[9]	4	80× 50 × 1.59	.667,.826,.889,1.081	6360m.m. ³
[13]	4	44× 56 × .8	1.575,2.45,3.5,5.2	1971.2m.m ³
[14]	3	85×85×1.57	2.1, 3.8, 5.3	11343.25 mm.
[15]	2	32× 30 × 3.175	1.56, 2.47	3048mm. ^{3048MM.}
Proposed Antenna	8	30× 50 × .8	1.165, 3.665, 4.605, 5.095, 6.01, 6.835, 8.045, 8.81	1200m.m. ³

3. ANTENNA DESIGN

Figure 1 shows the structure of modified e-slotted patch antenna, which consists of a five horizontal rectangular slots, and one rectangular vertical slot on the radiating patch, the proposed antenna design printed on glass epoxy substrate of relative permittivity ϵ_r 4.4, loss tangent .0013 and substrate height (h) is .8m.m. A microstrip line feed technique is use for giving the input power, as depicted in Figure 1, the feed line has a width $W_F = 3$ mm to achieve an impedance of 50Ω . The side view of proposed design shown in Figure 2. Due to multiple slots antenna resonate at different frequencies , first band resonate at 1.165 GHz cover the frequency band of 1.02-1.31 GHz for GPS system, second band resonant frequency is 3.665 GHz cover the frequency band 3.63-3.7 GHz for, forth band resonant frequency is 4.605 GHz cover the band 4.57-4.64 GHz for, 5.095 GHz cover the band 5.06-5.13 GHz for IEEE WLAN standards, 6.01 GHz cover the band 6.36-6.46 GHz, 6.835 GHz, 8.045 GHz cover 8.01-8.08 GHz, 8.81GHz,cover 8.76-8.86 GHz. The dimensions of proposed design given in Table 2 are optimum dimensions to obtained multi bands.

Figure 1. Top view of proposed design

Figure 2. Side view of proposed design

Table 2. Optimum dimensions of proposed design (all units in mm)

Paramerters	L_G	W_G	L_P	L_1	W_1	L_2	L_3	W_2
Dimensions	30	50	26	5	21	10	22.5	20
Paramerters	W_3	W_4	L_4	L_5	W_5	D	W_F	L_F
Dimensions	3	16	19.5	10	3	.5	3	3

4. ANALYSIS OF PROPOSED DESIGN

Rectangular patch is considered as a parallel combination of R_1 , L_1 C_1 as shown in Figure 3 according to cavity model, and the value of which are given as [16, 17]:

Figure 3. Equivalent circuit of rectangular patch

$$C_1 = \frac{\epsilon_{eff} \epsilon_0 L_P W_P \cos^{-2}(\pi y_0 / W_P)}{2h} \quad (1)$$

$$R_1 = \frac{Q_r}{\omega C_1} \quad (2)$$

$$L_1 = 1/\omega^2 C_1 \quad (3)$$

$$Q_r = \frac{c\sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}}}{8fh} \quad (4)$$

where C_1, R_1, L_1 are the fed rectangular patch antenna equivalent circuit parameters, Q_r is the total quality factor of the patch, f is the resonant frequency of the patch, L_P and W_P are the length and width of the rectangular patch, and h is the thickness of the substrate material, y_0 is the x co-ordinate of the feed point from the center.

Here $\omega = 2\pi f$ and ϵ_{eff} = effective permittivity of the medium which is given as [18, 19]:

$$\epsilon_{eff} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left(1 + 10h/W_P\right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

the resonant f of the fed patch is calculated as [20]:

$$f = \frac{c}{2L_P \sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}}} \quad (6)$$

where c = velocity of light in free space.

The impedance of fed patch according to the equivalent circuit is given as:

$$Z_{F1} = \left(\frac{1}{\frac{1}{R_1} + \frac{1}{j\omega L_1} + j\omega C_1} \right) \quad (7)$$

micro strip line is considered as the parallel combination of strip inductance L_{L1} and the strip capacitance C_{L1} as shown in Figure 4 is calculated as [21-26]:

$$C_{L1} = \sqrt{wW_f(130 \log(w/W_f) - 44)} pF \quad (8)$$

$$L_{L1} = h(40.5(w/W_f - 1) - 75 \log(w/W_f) + .2(w/W_f - 1)^2) nF$$

where W_f the width of feed strip, the microstrip line impedance Z_{L1} depends on strip inductance L_{L1} and strip capacitance C_{L1} is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Equivalent circuit for microstrip feed

total impedance of the strip is given as:

$$Z_{L1} = j\omega L_{L1} + \frac{1}{j\omega C_{L1} + \frac{1}{j\omega L_{L1}}} \quad (9)$$

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 5 shows the measured result of S11 impedance bandwidth below -10 dB return loss of proposed design at $h = .8\text{m.m.}$, and Figure 6 shows the comparison graph of measured result and simulated result of proposed design. The proposed design resonates at eight resonant frequencies, 1.165, 3.665, 4.605, 5.095, 6.01, 6.835, 8.045, 8.81 GHz in the simulated with the maximum return loss of -30 dB as shown in Figure 6. The effect of variation of substrate thickness (h) on number of resonant frequencies is also analyzed as shown in Figure 7.

The substrate thickness is varied from .8m.m. to 2m.m. at $h = .8\text{m.m.}$, 1.2m.m., 1.6m.m. and 2m.m. from the simulated result it is observed that at $h = .8\text{m.m.}$ antenna resonates at eight frequencies and maximum return loss -30 dB is achieved. While, at $h = 1.2\text{m.m.}$ antenna resonates at six frequencies, at $h = 1.6\text{m.m.}$ again antenna resonates at six frequencies, and $h = 2\text{m.m.}$ antenna resonates at three frequencies so it is observed as we increase the substrate thickness less band is obtained. Figure 8 represents the current distribution on the patch at different resonant frequency and the magnitude of the current is given in the table attached. It can be easily concluded with the current distribution that current is concentrated near the slots which has a significant effect on the impedance bandwidth. Table 3 shows distribution of eight bands of frequencies on which the proposed design resonates.

Figure 5. Measurement result of S11

Figure 6. Simulated and measured results S11 of proposed design

Figure 7. Simulated results of S11 at different thickness

Figure 8. Current distribution on the patch at different frequencies

Table3. Distribution of frequency bands

Frequency band No.	F_L (GHz)	F_H (GHz)	F_c (GHz)
1	1.02	1.31	1.165
2	3.63	3.7	3.665
3	4.57	4.64	4.605
4	5.06	5.13	5.095
5	5.97	6.05	6.01
6	6.76	6.91	6.835
7	8.01	8.08	8.045
8	8.76	8.86	8.81

6. CONCLUSION

A low profile, multi band antenna is successfully designed for various applications with good current distribution. The antenna designed is simple in structure and compact in nature. Eight bands of frequency are achieved with a simple structure. Also the effect of substrate thickness is studied and best result is obtained at 0.8 mm thickness which is low. Mathematical analysis of the designed is presented, the simulated result of s_{11} is in good agreement with the measured result. The antenna is better than many antennas exists in size, in number of bands and current distribution.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. A. Deschamps, "Microstrip microwave antennas," Proc. 3rd USAF symposium on antennas, 1953.
- [2] R. E. Munson, "Single slot cavity antennas assembly," U.S. patent no. 3713162, January 23, 1973.
- [3] R. E. Munson, "Conformal microstrip antennas and microstrip phased arrays," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propagation*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 74–78, 1974.
- [4] J. Q. Howell, "Microstrip Antennas," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 90–93, 1975.
- [5] I. J. Bahl, et al., "Microstrip Antennas," Dedham, MA: artech house, 1980.
- [6] Jyoti ranjan et al., "An F-shaped printed monopole antenna for dual-band RFID and WLAN applications," *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, vol. 53, no. 7, pp. 1478-1481, 2011
- [7] Mehr-e-Munir et al., "Multiband microstrip patch antenna using DGS for L-Band, s-band, c-band and mobile applications," *International Conference on Modern Problems of Radio Engineering, Telecommunications and Computer Science (TCSET)*, 2016.
- [8] Amit A. Deshmukha et al. "Triple band E-shaped Microstrip Antenna," *International conference on advances in computing & communications*, 2016.
- [9] A. A. deshmukh, K.P. Ray, "Stub loaded multiband slotted rectangular microstrip antennas," *IET microwave antennas and propagation*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 529-535, 2009.
- [10] Gehansami, et al. "Tri-band microstrip antenna design for wireless applications," *NRJAG Journal of Astronomy and Geophysics*, vol. 2, pp. 39-44, 2013.
- [11] Mirhamedrezvani, et al. "Design of multi-band microstrip antenna for wireless communications and ITU applications," *Natl. Acad. Sci. Lett.*, vol. 40, pp. 331–334, 2017.
- [12] A.R. Jalali, et al. compact multiband monopole "antenna for umts, wimax, and wlan applications," *microwave and optical technology letters*, vol. 58, no. 4, pp. 844-847, 2016.
- [13] Y. F. Cao et al. "A multi band slot antenna for GPS/Wimax/Wlan system," *IEEE transactions on antenna and propagation*, vol. 63, no. 3, pp. 952-958, 2015.
- [14] Edwin L., et al." A new triple band microstrip fractal antenna for C-band and S-band applications," *Journal of microwaves, optoelectronics and electromagnetic applications*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 210-224, 2016.
- [15] B. R. Sanjeeva et al. "Size miniaturization of slit-based circular patch antenna with defected ground structure," *Microwave and Optical Technology Letter*, vol. 57, no. 10, pp. 2410-2413, 2015
- [16] Akanksha gupta, et al. "Theoretical analysis of gap coupled microstrip antenna," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 567-576, 2017.
- [17] Tayfun gunel, "Modified resonant frequency calculation for e-shaped and h shaped microstrip patch antennas," *microwave and optical technology letters*, vol. 53, no. 10, pp. 2348-2351, 2011.
- [18] Vivek Singh "Anchor shape gap coupled patch antenna for WiMAX and WLAN applications," *The international journal for computation and mathematics in electrical and electronic engineering*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 263-286, 2019.
- [19] Xinglong Guo, et al. "Design and fabrication of miniaturized loop dual-band fractal antenna based on the silicon substrate," *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 363-365, 2008.
- [20] Ang Irene, et al. "An ultra-wideband stacked microstrip patch antenna," *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, vol. 49, no. 7, pp. 1659-1665, 2007.
- [21] K. P. Ray, et al. "Gap coupled rectangular microstrip antennas for dual and triple frequency operation," *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, vol. 49, no. 6, pp. 1480-1486, 2007.
- [22] N.T. Chang et al. "Enhance gain and bandwidth of circularly polarized microstrip patch antenna using gap-coupled method," *Progress in Electromagnetics Research, PIER* 96, pp. 128-139, 2009.
- [23] Binod Kumar Kanaujia, et al. "Analysis and design of gap coupled annular ring microstrip antenna," *International J. Antenna and propagation Hindawi*, pp. 1-5, 2015.
- [24] J.A. Ansari et al., "Analysis of shorting pin loaded half disk microstrip antenna for wideband operation", *Progress in Electromagnetics Research C*, vol 6, pp. 179–192, 2009.
- [25] P. Kumar et al. "Theoretical investigation of the input impedance of gap-coupled circular microstrip patch antenna," *J Infrared Milli Terahz Waves*, vol. 30, no. 11, pp. 1148–1160, 2009.
- [26] J. A. Ansari et al., "Analysis of a compact and broadband microstrip patch antenna," *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, vol. 50, no. 8, pp. 2059-2063, 2008.